

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 73

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 73

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 73:0 A Psalm of Asaph.</p>	
<p>Psa. 73:1 Surely God is ^agood to Israel,</p>	<p>Psa. 73:1 מִזְמוֹר לְאַסָּף אֵדָּן טוֹב לַיהוָה אֱלֹהִים לְבָרִי</p>
<p>To those who are ^bpure in heart! ² But as for me, ^amy feet came close to stumbling,</p>	<p>לֵבָב : ² וְאֲנִי כִמְעַט נָטוּי [נְטַיִו] רַגְלִי כְּאִין שִׁפְכָה</p>
<p>My steps ¹had almost slipped. ³ For I was ^aenvious of the ¹arrogant As I saw the ^bprosperity of the wicked.</p>	<p>[שִׁפְכוֹ] אֲשֶׁרֵי : ³ כִּי־קִנְיַתִּי בְּהוֹלְלִים שְׁלוֹם רְשָׁעִים</p>
<p>⁴ For there are no pains in their death, And their ¹body is fat.</p>	<p>אַרְאֶה : ⁴ כִּי אֵין חַרְצָבוֹת לְמוֹתָם וּבְרִיא אִוְלָם : ⁵</p>
<p>⁵ They are ^anot ¹in trouble as <i>other</i> ²men, Nor are they ^bplagued ³like mankind.</p>	<p>בְּעַמַּל אֲנוּשׁ אֵינָמוּ וְעַם־ אָדָם לֹא יִנְגַּעוּ : ⁶ לָכֵן</p>
<p>⁶ Therefore pride is ^atheir necklace; The ^bgarment of violence covers them.</p>	<p>בְּעִנְקֹתֵמוּ גִבּוֹהַ יַעֲטֹף־לְשִׁית חָמָס לָמוּ : ⁷ יֵצֵא מִחֶלֶב</p>
<p>⁷ Their eye ¹bulges from ^afatness; The imaginations of <i>their</i> heart ²run riot.</p>	<p>עֵינָמוּ עֲבָרוּ מִשִּׁפְכוֹת לֵבָב : ⁸ יִמְיָקוּ וְיִדְבְּרוּ בְרַע עֲשָׂק</p>
<p>⁸ They ^amock and ¹wickedly speak of oppression; They ^bspeak from on high.</p>	<p>מִפְרוֹם יִדְבְּרוּ : ⁹ שִׁתּוּ בְּשָׂמִים פִּיהֶם וּלְשׁוֹנָם</p>
<p>⁹ They have ^aset their mouth ¹against the heavens, And their tongue ²parades through the earth.</p>	<p>תִּהְלֹךְ בְּאַרְצֵי : ¹⁰ לָכֵן וַיָּשִׁיב [יָשׁוּב] עַמּוֹ הַלֵּם וַיְמִי מָלֵא</p>
<p>Psa. 73:10 Therefore ¹his people return to this place, And waters of ^aabundance are ²drunk by them.</p>	<p>יִמְצוּ לָמוּ : ¹¹ וַאֲמָרוּ אֵיכָה</p>

¹¹ They say, “How does God know?
And is there knowledge ¹with the
Most High?”

¹² Behold, “these are the wicked;
And always ^bat ease, they have
increased *in* wealth.

¹³ Surely ^ain vain I have ¹kept my
heart pure

And ^bwashed my hands in
innocence;

¹⁴ For I have been stricken ^aall day
long

And ^{1b}chastened every morning.

Psa. 73:15 If I had said, “I will speak
thus,”

Behold, I would have betrayed the
^ageneration of Your children.

¹⁶ When I ^apondered to understand
this,

It was ¹troublesome in my sight

¹⁷ Until I came into the ^{1a}sanctuary of
God;

Then I perceived their ^bend.

¹⁸ Surely You set them in ^aslippery
places;

You cast them down to
^{1b}destruction.

¹⁹ How they are ^{1a}destroyed in a
moment!

They are utterly swept away by
^bsudden terrors!

²⁰ Like a ^adream when one awakes,
O Lord, when ^baroused, You will
^cdespise their ¹form.

Psa. 73:21 When my ^aheart was
embittered

And I was ^bpierced ¹within,

²² Then I was ^asenseless and ignorant;
I was *like* ^{1a}a ^bbeast ²before You.

יָדַע-אֵל וַיֵּשׁ דַּעַה בְּעֵלְיוֹן :

12 הֲנִיחָה-אֱלֹהֵי רְשָׁעִים וְשִׁלּוּי

עוֹלָם הַשְּׂגוּר-חַיִל : 13 אֶךְ-

רִיק זַכִּיתִי לְבַבִּי וְאַרְחִץ

בְּנִקְיוֹן כַּפִּי : 14 וְאַתִּי נִגְוֵעַ

כָּל-הַיּוֹם וְתוֹכַחְתִּי

לְבִקְרִים : 15 אִם-אֶמְרֹתִי

אֶסְפְּרָה כִּמּוֹ הַנֵּחָה רוּר בְּנִיךְ

בְּגִדְתִּי : 16 וְאַחֲשָׁבָה לְדַעַת

זֹאת עֲמָל הִיא [הוּא]

בְּעֵינָי : 17 עַד-אֲבוֹא אֶל-

מִקְדָּשֵׁי-אֵל אֲבִינָה

לְאַחֲרֵיתָם : 18 אֶךְ בַּחֲלָקוֹת

תַּשִּׁית לָמוֹ הַפְּלִתָם

לְמִשׁוֹאוֹת : 19 אֵיךְ הָיוּ

לְשֹׁמֵה כְּרֹגַע סָפוּ תָמוּ מִן-

בְּלָהוֹת : 20 כַּחֲלוֹם מִהֲקִיץ

אֲדַנִּי בְּעִיר אֲצַלְמָם תִּבְזָה :

21 כִּי יִתְחַמֵּץ לְבַבִּי וְכִלְיוֹתַי

אֶשְׁתּוֹנֵן : 22 וְאַנִּי-בְּעַר וְלֹא

אֲדַע בְּהִמּוֹת הַיָּתִי עֲמָךְ : 23

וְאַנִּי תָמִיד עֲמָךְ אֲחִזֶּזָה בְּיַד-

יְמִינִי : 24 בְּעֲצָתְךָ תִּנְחַנְנִי

²³ Nevertheless "I am continually with You;

You have taken hold of my right hand.

²⁴ With Your counsel You will "guide me,

And afterward ^breceive me ¹to glory.

Psa. 73:25 "Whom have I in heaven *but You?*

And ¹besides You, I desire nothing on earth.

²⁶ My "flesh and my heart may fail,
But God is the ¹strength of my heart and my ^bportion forever.

²⁷ For, behold, "those who are far from You will ^bperish;

You have ¹destroyed all those who ^{2c}are unfaithful to You.

²⁸ But as for me, "the nearness of God is my good;

I have made the Lord ¹GOD my ^brefuge,

That I may "tell of all Your works.

וְאַחַר כְּבוֹד תִּקְחֵנִי : ²⁵ מִי-

לִי בַשָּׁמַיִם וְעַמֶּךָ לֹא-

חֲפֹצְתִי בָאָרֶץ : ²⁶ כָּלָה

שְׂאֵרֵי וּלְבָבִי צוּר-לְבָבִי

וַחֲלָקֵי אֱלֹהִים לְעוֹלָם : ²⁷

כִּי-הִנֵּה רַחֲמֶיךָ יֹאבְדוּ

הַצְמִתָּה כָּל-זוֹנֵה מִמֶּנֶּךָ : ²⁸

וְאַנִּי אֶקְרַבֶּת אֱלֹהִים לִי-

טוֹב שְׂתִי אִבְאֹלְנִי יְהוָה

מִחֲסִי לְסֹפֵר כָּל-

מַלְאֲכֹתֶיךָ :

References

Psalm 73:1

^aPs 86:5

^bPs 24:4; 51:10; Matt 5:8

Psalm 73:2

¹Lit *were caused to slip*

^aPs 94:18

Psalm 73:3

¹Or *boasters*

^aPs 37:1; Prov 23:17

^bJob 21:7; Ps 37:7; Jer 12:1

Psalm 73:4

¹Or *belly*

Psalm 73:5

¹Lit *in the trouble of men*

²Or *mortals*

³Lit *with*

^aJob 21:9; Ps 73:12

^bPs 73:14

Psalm 73:6

^aGen 41:42; Prov 1:9

^bPs 109:18

Psalm 73:7

¹Lit *goes forth*

²Lit *overflow*

^aJob 15:27; Ps 17:10; Jer 5:28

Psalm 73:8

¹Or *they speak in wickedness; From on high they speak of oppression*

^aPs 1:1

^bPs 17:10; 2 Pet 2:18; Jude 16

Psalm 73:9

¹Or *in*

²Lit *walks*

^aRev 13:6

Psalm 73:10

¹Or *His*

²Lit *drained out*

^aPs 23:5

Psalm 73:11

¹Lit *in*

^aJob 22:13

Psalm 73:12

^aPs 49:6; 52:7

^bJer 49:31; Ezek 23:42

Psalm 73:13

¹Or *cleansed my heart*

^aJob 21:15; 34:9; 35:3

^bPs 26:6

Psalm 73:14

¹Lit *my chastening*

^aPs 38:6

^bJob 33:19; Ps 118:18

Psalm 73:15

^aPs 14:5

Psalm 73:16

¹Lit *labor, trouble*

^aEccl 8:17

Psalm 73:17

¹Lit *sanctuaries*

^aPs 27:4; 77:13

^bPs 37:38

Psalm 73:18

¹Lit *ruins*

^aPs 35:6

^bPs 35:8; 36:12

Psalm 73:19

¹Lit *become a desolation*

^aNum 16:21; Is 47:11

^bJob 18:11

Psalm 73:20

¹Or *image*

^aJob 20:8

^bPs 78:65

^c1 Sam 2:30

Psalm 73:21

¹Lit *in my kidneys*

^aJudg 10:16

^bActs 2:37

Psalm 73:22

¹Or *an animal*

²Lit *with You*

^aPs 49:10; 92:6

^bJob 18:3; Ps 49:20; Eccl 3:18

Psalm 73:23

^aPs 16:8

Psalm 73:24

¹Or *with honor*

^aPs 32:8; 48:14; Is 58:11

^bGen 5:24; Ps 49:15

Psalm 73:25

¹Or *with*

^aPs 16:2; Phil 3:8

Psalm 73:26

¹Lit *rock*

^aPs 38:10; 40:12; 84:2; 119:81

^bPs 16:5

Psalm 73:27

¹Or *silenced*

²Lit *go to a whoring from*

^aPs 119:155

^bPs 37:20

^cEx 34:15; Num 15:39; Ps 106:39; Hos 4:12; 9:1

Psalm 73:28

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

^aPs 65:4; Heb 10:22; James 4:8

^bPs 14:6; 71:7

^cPs 40:5; 107:22; 118:17

Targum

Psa. 73:1 A psalm composed by Asaph. Truly, God is good to Israel, to the pure of heart. ² But I – my feet had almost slipped; my steps had all but faltered. ³ For I became jealous of the mockers whenever I would see the welfare of the wicked. ⁴ For they are not dismayed and daunted by the day of their death; their opinions are sought out, and their heart is fat and strong. ⁵ They do not toil with the toil of men who are occupied with Torah; and they are not smitten with the righteous sons of men who endure sufferings. ⁶ Because of this, pride has adorned them, a crown that they place on their heads because of their rapacity. ⁷ Their faces are distorted by fat; their carvings have transgressed, the heart is ashamed. ⁸ They will decay because of fatness; and they will speak to cause harm and to oppress; they will speak from the arrogance of their heart. ⁹ They have set their mouth against the holy ones of heaven; and their tongue flares against the holy ones of the earth. ¹⁰ Then he turns against the people of the LORD, to rule them; and they will smite them with hammers, and cause many tears to flow from them. ¹¹ And they will say, “How then does God know, and is there knowledge in the Most High?” ¹² Behold, these are the wicked who dwell securely in this age; they have acquired property, they have procured wealth. ¹³ Truly, in vain have I purified my heart, and washed my hands in purity. ¹⁴ And I have been smitten all the day; and my admonition [has come] with every dawn. ¹⁵ If I said, “I will talk like them” – behold, I would have done evil to the generation of your children. ¹⁶ And I thought to know this, [but] it is a weariness in my sight – ¹⁷ Until the time of redemption, when I come to the sanctuaries of God, I will understand their fate. ¹⁸ Truly, you have placed them in dark places, you have thrown them into the wasteland. ¹⁹ How they have become a desolation in a moment! They are finished, destroyed because of chaos. ²⁰ Like a dream of a man who awakes: the LORD in the great day of judgment, when they awake from their graves; in anger you will despise their likeness. ²¹ For my heart will feel pain, and my kidneys burn like fire. ²² And I am a fool, and I do not know; I was reckoned as a beast with you. ²³ But I am continually with you; you have grasped my right hand. ²⁴ You will guide me by your counsel; and after the glory that you commanded to come upon me is complete, you will take me. ²⁵ Who, like you, is mine in heaven, but you? And besides you I desire no friend on earth. ²⁶ My body and my heart are destroyed; God is the Mighty One who tries my heart and my portion forever. ²⁷ For behold, the wicked who are far from you will perish; you have destroyed all who stray from the fear of you. ²⁸ But I – to be near to the LORD is good to me; I have placed my confidence in the LORD God, to tell to all the righteous the commandments of your charge. --

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is the first one of the third book of Psalms. The first two books deal with personal pleas, mainly from King David. The last two books are concerned with universal themes demonstrating the LORD's goodness. The introduction of this Psalm, an eloquent theme of the LORD, is always good to Israel. The psalmist surveyed Jewish history and beheld much misery for the LORD's people. At the same time, evil men flourished. Why does the way of the wicked prosper (Jeremiah 12:1)?

The writer Assaf said that everything the LORD does to Israel is good. The LORD caused suffering at times so that the fruits of good deeds may be preserved for the future world of reward. The sages Radak and Rashi agree.

Another view would be that the nations of the world were jealous that the LORD gave Israel the Promised Land and allowed the nation to prosper in the diaspora. The gentile nations of the world have tried for millennia to destroy Israel. However, the LORD would not let it happen.

Verse two

The author had almost turned away from the LORD. He had difficulty understanding the bad things that happened to Israel. Where is the LORD's justice when evil is snuffing out good? It is difficult to maintain faith in the LORD when persecution from the gentile nations is occurring.

But as for me, my feet had almost turned away, but little, and my steps would have been poured out.

Verse six

Evil men and women wear their evil as an ornament around their necks. This is seen today when certain people grab power in synagogues and churches. They forget that they should be concerned for the worship of the LORD and the betterment of the congregation. The leaders who grab power through evil will force the people to give them the respect they do not deserve and should not be given. The violence in synagogues and churches is passive-aggressive attitudes, backstabbing, and false gossip.

Therefore pride is the ornament around their necks; their form enwraps itself in violence.

Verse ten

Sadly, evil people show that they do not believe in the LORD. They grab their human authority and exploit it to get their way and power to control others. They take advantage of people by pretending to give them something good. Evil people convince good people to follow them.

Therefore, His people, too, turn thither again, and the waters of abundance will be tasted by them also.

Verse seventeen

Persons who accept and demonstrate the Torah shall become the bearers of the LORD's glory.

Until I entered into the sanctuaries of God and learned to look for their end, then I would become a bearer of the LORD's own glory.

Verse eighteen

Making a person's path smooth, the LORD let them fall prey to deceptions, to hopes remaining forever unfulfilled. The LORD places trouble in people's paths so that they can recognize evil when it confronts them. Suppose people believe that everything is positive and wonderful. In that case, they will be deceived by evil people and may commit evil themselves, thinking it is good. This is an answer to why bad things happen to good people.

You set them only on smooth places (and paths), but by doing so, You have let them fall prey to deception. Evil will overtake a person who does not experience what evil is.

Verse twenty-two

When a person's heart is embittered, their baser passions come to the surface.

Then I am a creature devoid of reason and shall not acquire understanding. So beast-like was I before You.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

